

SUPPORTING INFORMATION - APPENDIX S1

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PHENOTYPIC SIMILARITY LEADS TO TAXONOMIC INCONSISTENCY: A REVISION OF THE LOWLAND'S ANTPITTAS

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Family Grallariidae

***Cryptopezus* gen. n.**

Type species. *Grallaria nattereri* Pinto, 1937 by original description.

Included species. *Cryptopezus nattereri* (Pinto, 1937) comb. nov. Speckle-breasted Antpitta.

Diagnosis. Distinguished from other genera in Grallariidae by breast, upper belly and flanks spotted dusky, forming a particular pattern that is fully distinguishable from stripes and spots present on the other species of lowland's antpittas; bare orbital skin buffy white. Longer tarsi than *Hylopezus* sensu stricto and shorter tarsi than *Myrmothera* sensu lato. Genetically distinct. Loudsongs structurally distinct, show whistled notes, steadily increasing in amplitude, first few slightly falling, but thereafter rising in pitch from c. 2 to c. 2.5 kHz, notes changing shape through the series. Habitat: Ground and lower growth in humid and montane forest, mature secondary woodland, and borders; often in very densely tangled vegetation and bamboo.

Distribution: Restricted to the southern Atlantic Forest between 1200–1900 m, but it may occur

at lower elevations in the southern part of its range.

Etymology. The masculine generic name is taken from the Greek *kryptós* (hidden) and *pezos* (walking, that walks) < *patéō* (to walk, to step), meaning “the one that walks hidden.”

This name is an allusion to the secretive habits and the difficulty of locating this bird even when it is active and vocalizing.

Origin and phenotypic evolution. The origin of *Cryptopezus* predates that of its closest relatives and was estimated as dating back to the Early Miocene (Fig. 1). Recent studies showed that the Atlantic Forest holds ancient lineages that date to the mid-Tertiary, as verified for birds (Derryberry et al., 2011), mammals (Fabre, Galewski, Tilak, & Douzery, 2013; Galewski, Mauffrey, Leite, Patton, & Douzery, 2005) and frogs (Fouquet et al., 2012). This endemic Atlantic Forest lineage seems to have originated from Andean ancestors, and probably reached southeastern South America through the southern Andes, as it is restricted to humid subtropical and montane forests (Krabbe & Schulenberg, 2003). Given the phylogenetic distance recovered between *Cryptopezus* and *H. ochroleucus*, their phenotypic similarities seem to be result of either convergence or retention of ancestral characters (Carneiro et al., 2018). These results can also be related to the broad variation of the phenotypic measurements of these lineages (Tables 1 and 2), or to the niche conservatism reported for some Grallariidae species (Stratford & Stouffer, 2015).

***Hylopezus* Ridgway, 1909**

Type species. *Hylopezus perspicillatus* (Lawrence, 1861)._

Included species. *Hylopezus perspicillatus* (Lawrence, 1861) Streak-chested Antpitta.

Hylopezus auricularis (Gyldenstolpe, 1941) Masked Antpitta.

Hylopezus macularius (Temminck, 1830) Spotted Antpitta.

Hylopezus paraensis (Sneathlage, 1910) Sneathlage’s Antpitta.

Hylopezus dilutus (Hellmayr, 1910). Zimmer’s Antpitta.

Hylopezus whittakeri Carneiro et al., 2012 Alta Floresta Antpitta.

Hylopezus ochroleucus (Wied, 1831). White-browed Antpitta.

Diagnosis. Distinguished from other genera by mantle with conspicuous shaft-streaks, more olivaceous upperparts, much paler ochraceous subterminal bands of pectoral spots, and wingbars occupying the entire length of the wing. Genetically distinct. Habitat: Floor and dense undergrowth of forest, lower undergrowth of humid forest, semi-deciduous and deciduous woodland, including *caatinga* woodland.

Myrmothera Vieillot, 1816

Type species. *Myrmornim campanisonam* (Hermann, 1783)._

Included species. *Myrmothera campanisona* (Hermann, 1783) Thrush-like Antpitta.

Myrmothera subcanescens Todd, 1927 Tapajós Antpitta

Myrmothera simplex (Salvin & Godman, 1884) Tepui Antpitta.

Myrmothera dives (Salvin, 1865) Thicket Antpitta.

Myrmothera fulviventris (Sclater, 1858) White-lored Antpitta.

Myrmothera berlepschi (Hellmayr, 1903). Amazonian Antpitta.

Diagnosis. Distinguished from other genera by a buffy loreal spot; entire upperparts olive-brown, outer webs of primaries paler; mantle without shaft-streaks, breast and upper belly with particular patterns of streak. Genetically distinct. Loudsongs structurally distinct. Habitat: Floor and lower part of very dense undergrowth at forest edge and in overgrown clearings.